

COMPUTER VISION BASED 24X7 CATTLE HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

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Abstract

Advanced computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are driving a revolution in cattle health monitoring and automation of traditional cattle rearing methods. Smart farming techniques and automation may improve cattle welfare, sustainability, and farmer productivity. These developments improve product quality, save expenses, and do away with time-consuming procedures. In order to solve resource restrictions and food security, intelligent farming is becoming more and more popular as the world's population grows. Our proposed embedded computer vision based cattle monitoring system use CNN model for training the data and send alert message to anomalies if abnormal occurs. IoT and data analytics replace antiquated wireless sensor networks to maximize farming output. Exceptionally low latency, bandwidth optimization, assurance, and real-time analytics are some of the benefits of cloud computing.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Artificial Intelligence, IoT, smart farming, CNN

Introduction

Traditional methods of evaluating the health of cattle are costly and inefficient. They only provide partial data and result in significant expenditures for both manpower and technology advancements [1]. An effective reporting system helps to plan for and raise awareness of cattle diseases, reduce financial losses, and increase productivity in the production of meat, and dairy products [2]. The era of Agriculture 4.0, which places a greater emphasis on intelligence and automation, began with the use of IoT and cognitive computing technologies in farming [3]. By enabling remote farmers to access biological and ecological data, the Internet of Things (IoT) will surely transform cattle management. It is possible that this innovation will reduce labor cost[4]. IoT enhances farming operations' automation and real-time monitoring, which reduces labor costs and promotes sustainability by using state-of-the-art technologies [5].

IoT technology ensures accurate pH monitoring by capturing, analyzing, and interpreting real-time data on rumen acidification in cattle to track data control by documenting behaviors and dietary parameters, which is crucial for the health of the animals and herd [6]. Farm automation

and nanotechnology plays a vital role in the economical and efficient management of cattle on farms, reducing the need for the man power [7]. Researchers have used wireless sensor nodes with pH monitoring equipment to assess rumen conditions. However, the reference electrode's poor capacity adds to the short lifespan of these nodes [8]. Cattle rearers can better understand the unique needs of each cattle and identify the issues early on by integrating sensors and computer algorithms into farming for real-time, uninterrupted control and surveillance systems [9]. On-farm and point-of-care technologies are revolutionizing cattle operations, reducing economic losses, minimizing antibiotic treatments, enabling the early diagnosis of transmissible infections, and enhancing the general health of cattle [10].

The combination of sensor technologies and computer vision in cow health surveillance has improved the overall cattle health monitoring system. Accurately identifying individual animals is a major challenge when using computer vision for cattle monitoring, especially in complex and dynamic environments. Cattle health monitoring by sensors and computer vision has advanced significantly, although these technologies are still in their infancy. It will take interdisciplinary cooperation and consistent innovation to address the identified research gaps. With an emphasis on technology, the internet, communication, and data storage, the study examines an ecosystem for agriculture that is built on sensors and vision. It encompasses advantages, difficulties, upcoming advancements, and prospects.

Innovative Cattle Health monitoring

The need of cattle monitoring and the challenges in this system are health monitoring, cattle theft, and early disease detection to reduce the risk of death and financial loss [11]. Precision agriculture closely monitors the development, behavior, well-being, and productivity of cattle in real time by combining information, algorithms, engineering, livestock and veterinary sciences, and physiological processes. This makes it possible for farmers to quickly make informed decisions [12]. Maintaining productivity requires having access to reliable, farm-specific, real-time information. But this knowledge is frequently shared and given one-on-one. Therefore, using automated, targeted, and economical methods becomes crucial for precise data collection and transmission. [13].

Noval methods for tracking the cattle diseases are real-time PCR, DNA analysis, and restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP). To carry out precise diagnosis and supervision, these operations require knowledge and access to modern laboratory facilities [14]. A time-driven embedded sensor is used in a novel method that combines an Inertial Measurement Unit with

a Machine Learning (ML) model to accurately track and categorize dairy cattle activities [15]. The most recent research investigates preventing infection with the use of Internet of Things (IoT) sensors that gather data in real time and store it in cloud-based storage devices. Users' identities are determined from the data being collected, and they receive notifications through screening and statistical analysis [16]. By identifying anomalies in cattle behavior linked to conditions like lameness, the integration of IoT and data analytics has the potential to drastically alter the cattle industry [17]. The development of a cattle health diagnosis algorithm makes use of an intelligent harness's capabilities to accurately assess the health of the animals, providing farmers with useful data for their decision-making [18].

Farming, disease prevention, meat product authenticity, and reducing false insurance claims all depend on accurate cow individual identification. In order to distinguish cattle faces and detect facial emotions, computational imaging technologies are used [19]. By reducing expenses, getting rid of waste, and lowering labor demand, smart farming supports farming operations. It uses ICT and sensor data to speed up the adoption of technology advancements like big data and machine learning [20]. Fog and edge computing are becoming more and more popular for farming applications as a replacement for cloud computing. In smart farming, edge computing has strong capabilities that allow for data-driven decision-making and real-time monitoring. [21].

Sensors for cattle health monitoring

The sensor-based cow monitoring system tracks activity patterns using an accelerometer. Monitoring the health of cattle and improving farm management decisions depend heavily on this data. The device utilises machine learning to categorise behavioural states, like rumination, and wirelessly archives health-related data. This helps farmers identify diseases early because unwell cattle tend to have higher temperatures and less rumination. This invention seeks to enhance cow health management and reduce farmers' workload. Numerous sensors are used in the suggested cattle monitoring system, such as a thermistor for temperature monitoring, an accelerometer for activity detection, and a photoplethysmography sensor for heart rate and oxygen saturation measurements. Additionally, it has a GPS module for tracking its whereabouts. These sensors gather data, which is then sent to a server via an ESP32-based board with built-in Wi-Fi. This allows for real-time monitoring and analysis, which is consistent with the precision livestock farming paradigm, which aims to improve animal welfare and productivity.[22].

Sensor-based cow monitoring systems classify the behaviour of cattle using machine learning and deep learning algorithms by using sensors that are affixed to the animals to collect raw data. This method improves farmers' comprehension of the demands of individual animals, leading to increased productivity and efficiency in the management of livestock. The ResNeXt model, a deep residual neural network that was presented in the study, outperformed other baseline models in the field and obtained an excellent average accuracy of 94.96% in classifying cow behaviour[23]. Vital indications like body temperature, heart rate, and daily steps are tracked by the bovine iCare Monitoring System (CIMS). To collect these vitals, it makes use of a pedometer strap and collar belt with built-in sensors. In order to help identify early indicators of disease in cattle, the data is presented via a mobile application that also categorises the vitals into Alert Levels (Normal, Alert Level 1, Alert Level 2, and Alert Level 3)[24]. The creation of a leg-worn sensor-based system focus on integrating the concepts of animal-computer interaction (ACI). By continuously gathering physiological and behavioural data, this technology allows for real-time monitoring, meeting the demands of farmers and animals alike. The design approach integrates both software and hardware components, demonstrating how wearable sensor technology may revolutionise cow health monitoring procedures while balancing cutting-edge technology with pragmatic farm realities[25].

Internet of Things (IoT)-based cattle health monitoring system that uses wireless sensors for continuous monitoring of dairy cow health. By allowing farmers to remotely monitor the location and health of their animals, this method seeks to improve dairy production. It highlights how crucial automated wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are to agricultural optimisation since they offer a low-cost way to identify diseases and lessen the need for human intervention, which eventually improves farm management techniques and boosts milk production[26]. An Internet of Things (IoT)-based sensor-based livestock monitoring system which contain Raspberry Pi Module 4B, RFID Card Reader, Arduino Microphone Module, DHT11 Sensor, Arduino UNO, Neo-6M GPS Sensor, and Heartbeat Sensor with the ultimate goal of improving bovine well-being and streamlining shed management, allows real-time monitoring of environmental variables as well as individual cow parameters including location, frequency of milking, and heartbeat fluctuations[27].

Proposed Methodology

Computer vision based image acquisition is proposed for monitoring 24x7 inshed cattles. The image is acquired by using an embedded camera system for in-shed cattle monitoring. The

camera should be compact, reliable and can operate in challenging environments (low light, dust, vibration), and possibly support real-time image processing (e.g., health monitoring, movement tracking, feed behavior analysis). The objective of using embedded camera is to monitor animal detection and counting, health and posture analysis, feed behaviour, estrus or lameness detection, environmental monitoring. Then select the camera based on budget, power and processing need. Setup the hardware, install the software and develop the image processing pipeline.

Fig: Image capturing and training in cattle monitoring system

The figure 1 shows the process of image capturing, analysis, training and notification of our proposed system. After setting the image processing pipeline, deploy the CNN based algorithm for training the model. Creating a CNN-based predictive model for an in-shed cattle monitoring system involves designing a Convolutional Neural Network that can learn from images or video frames to detect behaviors, predict health issues, or monitor conditions such as feeding, lying, or lameness.

Fig 2: Computer vision based cattle health monitoring

To evaluate and optimize the model confusion matrices is used. A confusion matrix is a key evaluation tool for classification models—especially useful for cattle monitoring system to understand how well our CNN is distinguishing between normal and abnormal conditions. The below confusion matrix shows the comparison between true labels and predicted labels, structured for a 4-class problem:

	Pred: Feeding	Pred: Lying	Pred: Walking	Pred: Standing
True: Feeding	50	2	3	1
True: Lying	1	46	2	1
True: Walking	3	4	40	3
True: Standing	2	0	5	43

Table 1: Each row represents the actual class, and each column the predicted class.

Diagonal values = correct predictions

Off-diagonal = misclassifications

Once the model is trained, store video/images locally or stream to cloud. Send real-time alerts via SMS/email for anomalies also visualize trends with dashboards.

Data Type	Visualization Type	Purpose
Body temperature trends	Line chart per animal or herd	Spot fever or disease onset
GPS movement tracking	Geospatial heat map	Identify grazing patterns or lost animals
Milk production over time	Multi-line chart or bar chart	Compare yield across cows or periods
Activity levels	Stacked bar or area chart	Detect anomalies in movement
Feeding and rumination	Radar or pie chart per cow	Visualize balance of behavior
Health alerts	Dashboard with color-coded cards	Instant at-a-glance alerts

Table 2: Visualization types

Creating data visualizations for a cattle monitoring system help in understanding animal health, behavior, and farm operations at a glance.

Conclusion

A computer vision-based cattle monitoring system represents a transformative step forward in precision cattle farming. By leveraging advanced imaging technologies and machine learning algorithms, this enable continuous, non-invasive monitoring of cattle to detect health issues, track behavior, and improve farm efficiency. Key capabilities like posture recognition, activity tracking, body condition scoring, and early disease detection help farmers make timely, data-driven decisions.

Compared to traditional manual methods, computer vision reduces labor costs, minimizes human error, and provides real-time insights at scale. As the agricultural industry faces challenges related to labor shortages, sustainability, and animal welfare, integrating computer vision into cattle management offers a scalable and intelligent solution. computer vision not only improves cattle welfare and farm profitability but also plays a vital role in shaping the future of smart, sustainable agriculture.

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